

Relationship Between Lagrangian Theory, Quadratic Forms and Special Relativity for a Free Particle

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We suggest that if one considers: $\partial L/\partial v = p$ and $H=E = pv - L$, where L is the Lagrangian and H , the Hamiltonian for a free particle, then this theory is consistent with a quadratic relationship between E and p . This may then be mapped to a 2x2 Lorentz transformation of $(0, m_0)$ ($c=1$) to (p, E) such that the quadratic form is linked to the Lorentz transformation. In other words, p must be proportional to v and so dL/dv suggests a quadratic term in v .

Lagrangian Theory

We consider two main ideas from Lagrangian theory. First:

$P = \text{momentum} = \partial L/\partial v$ (one dimension here) ((1)).

We only consider cases in which this second condition holds:

$E = H = pv - L$ ((2))

We focus on a free particle which has constant E and v and p . We also assume that p is proportional to v as this is the nature of momentum.

((2)) is already in the form of a quadratic if v/L goes as p and E/L as EE . From ((1)), we may consider: $L = m_0 v^2/2 + \text{constant}$ so that: $\partial L/\partial v = m_0 v$ which is consistent with the ideas applied to ((2)).

Thus, we see that Lagrangian formalism (at least for a free particle with ((2)) assumed to hold) is consistent with a quadratic theory.

If one has a particle with rest mass, m_0 , at rest in one frame, this may be seen as sets of (p, E) ($c=1$) from other frames moving with constant $-v$. This suggests that one consider special relativity and see if there is any link to the above considerations.

Special Relativity

It is well-known that a 2x2 Lorentz transformation changes $(0, m_0)$ to (p, E) ($c=1$), where the matrix is:

$$\begin{vmatrix} g(v) & v g(v) \\ v g(v) & g(v) \end{vmatrix} \quad ((3)) \quad \text{Here } g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$$

Given that $p = mv / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ and $dL/dv = p = mv / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$, one may propose that:

L is $-m_0 c^2 \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$. Then: $L dL/dv = m_0 m v$ or $p = mv / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$.

At this point, the minus sign is not needed for L , but it becomes necessary if one tries to meet condition ((2)) i.e.

$$E = pv - L = pv + m_0 c^2 \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \rightarrow E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4 \quad (4)$$

Thus, there is a direct link between a quadratic form associated with a Lagrangian and special relativity.

Conclusion

We suggest that two main features of Lagrangian theory, namely ((1)) and ((2)), applied to a free particle with constant v , p , E suggest a quadratic form. We try to link this form to special relativity to show the exact value of L from the point of view of special relativity.